

A Qualitative Study on the Role of Society in Implementing Sustainable Development Goals.

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Abstract:

Sustainable development means attaining a balance between environmental protection and human economic development and between the present and future needs. It means equity in development and sectorial actions across space and time. It requires an integration of economic, social and environmental approaches towards development. In Vellore Citizens Welfare Forum Union of India and in M.C Mehta v. Union of India, it was observed that the balance between environmental protection and developmental activities could only be maintained by strictly following the principle of 'sustainable development. This is a development strategy that caters the needs of the present without negotiating the ability of upcoming generations to satisfy their needs. The present study provides a guideless for each and every citizen in a society to be part of attaining sustainable development goals.

Introduction

What is sustainable development goals?
"Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present, without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs."

The concept of sustainable development can be interpreted in many different ways, but at its core is an approach to development that looks to balance different, and often competing, needs against an awareness of the environmental, social and economic limitations we face as a society.

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was adopted at the United Nations Summit in New York from 25 to 27 September 2015. The Agenda is a broad and universal policy agenda, with 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with 169 associated targets which are integrated and indivisible. Building on the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the 2030 Agenda seeks to guide Member States to transform their approach to achieve inclusive, people-centered and sustainable development with no one left behind.

B. Why sustainable development goals

Sustainable development encourages us to conserve and enhance our resource base, by gradually changing the ways in which we develop and use technologies. Countries must be allowed to meet their basic needs of employment, food, energy, water and sanitation.

If this is to be done in a sustainable manner, then there is a definite need for a sustainable level of population. Economic growth should be supported and developing nations should be allowed a growth of equal quality to the developed nations.

Objectives Of The Study

The objectives of present study are:

- To understand the present status and trends of E-Commerce;
- To identify benefits of E-commerce
- To know challenges of E-commerce.
- To discuss the future of E-Commerce in India

Research Methodology

The paper has been written on the basis of secondary data. The secondary data were collected from published books, journals, research papers, magazines, daily newspaper, internet

and official statistical documents. The study is qualitative in nature.

Role Of The Society

Reduce (not waste resources)

Avoid commercial mail; Delete from the databases of advertising companies.

Avoid electric devices and toys with batteries.

Avoid elevators whenever possible.

Congratulate, communicate and call meetings electronically.

Consume seasonal and organic farming products.

Control water consumption in hygiene, irrigation and swimming pools.

Cook efficiently: take advantage of waste heat, do not heat more water than necessary and do not preheat in the oven if it is not necessary.

Defrost the refrigerator regularly, check that the doors close properly, and check boilers and heaters.

Do not get carried away by commercial campaigns

Do not program very high temperatures (warm more) or excessively low (ventilate better, use awnings, blinds...); use timer and place thermostats in appropriate places.

Incorporate water saving devices in taps and tanks.

Load washers, dishwashers, etc. properly

Organize movements of several people in the same vehicle.

Proceed to drip irrigation, water first and last hours of the day.

Quick shower; Close taps while brushing, shaving or lathering.

Reduce (better avoid!) The use of plastics, cans, objects with batteries, materials with toxic substances, etc.

Reuse everything you can

In particular, avoid plastic bags and wrappers, aluminum foil and paper cups.

Print, for example, on paper already used on one side.

Rehabilitate homes, make them more sustainable (better insulation, etc.) avoiding new construction)

Replace them with reusable, repairing them when necessary, while you can use recycled products (paper, toner...) and recyclable.

Reuse paper.

Reuse water: use water from washing fruits and vegetables and cooking eggs (enriched with calcium) to water the plant.

Recycle

Do not buy products without ensuring their safety: monitor the composition of food, cleaning products, clothing... and avoid those that do not offer guarantees Opt for renewable energy in the home, automotive, etc.

Use devices that work with solar energy: radios, mobile chargers, laptops.

Use efficient appliances, low consumption and low pollution (A ++)

Contribute to education and citizen action

Contribute to environmentalist the workplace, the neighborhood and city where we live.

Help conceive sustainability measures as an improvement that guarantees everyone's future and not as a limitation.

Claim clear information policies on all problems.

Claim local, state and universal legislation for the protection of the "Cyber-interact" means: Support solidarity and sustainability campaigns from the computer.

Claim the solidarity tax application.

Conclusion

This is a critical moment in earth's history, a time when humanity must choose its future. Our planet earth is perhaps the only human habitat in the vast universe and we owe it to posterity to preserve the divine heritage of our biosphere without pollution,

degradation and destruction. The long term perspective for sustainable development requires the broad-based participation of various stakeholders in policy formulation, decision-making and implementation at all levels. Efforts must be made, especially by developing countries, to work towards synergizing experiences and raising shared regional concerns as a strong united front in international forums. Mechanisms must be put in place to facilitate such international exchange of domestic and global experiences in sustainable development.

Reference

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